

EXAMINING THE AUDACITY OF CHARLES DARWIN'S EVOLUTIONARY THEORY ON MORALITY AND PSEUDO- CHRISTIANITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract

There has been a long-time debate on whether Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory has actually influenced Christianity, moral ethics and political thinking or not. While some opined that his book on evolution gave birth to the audacity of the present wave of moral bankruptcy and decadence in the society, others are of the view that men can live without God as his theory questioned the omniscience and the omnipotence nature of God over creation in its application. The paper pointed out how Charles Darwin's theory has shaped and changed the entire world to the level of questioning the authority of God on earth; which led to the questioning of the Holy Book, morality, fidelity and the sanctity of lives and the ethics of marriage in the modern world. To achieve these, qualitative research method was adopted in sequentially consulting secondary sources of information in the library, books, achieves, journals, newspapers, bulletins among others. The paper observed that Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of 1859 has had a damaging influence on Christianity and morality especially among the German's scholars and soldiers like Hitler, Friedrich Ratzel, Sir Helford Mackinder, and General Karl Haushofer a general in the German army. The paper propounded the concept of mind mutation which says: the mind infinitely mutates infinitely towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting(mutating) to it infinitely be it good or bad. The paper concluded by asking: 'Will morality and Christianity be eroded and the world will not be brought to its knees with the survival of the fittest theory of Charles Darwin? Shouldn't there be accepted moral ethics, laws and justice that governs and favor all?'

Keywords: Audacity, Evolutionary, Theory, Morality, Pseudo-Christianity, International Relations

Introduction

Christianity and morality and in fact, all known religion, points to the need to order society and bring about justice, fairness and equity. According to Oaikhena (2022) he rightly observed that “morality is the health of a society, that a society plagued with immorality is a sick society”. In the same vein, distinctive difference was established between human and animals with man as higher being with dominion over other creation. In trying to achieve this societal order, all known religion be it Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism or African Traditional Religion (ATR) have at its core values; the sanctity of life, the concept of judgment after death, repentance, forgiveness, holy living, love for one another and the law of sowing and reaping which points to judgment or Karma and this birthed idealism and realism which has long history in international relations. This has also led to intentional or obvious harmful attitudes or behavior towards a party because of their identity, (e.g. race, religion, sexual orientation, etc (Oaikhena, 2022)

Today, Christianity and morality is under siege as a new world order was birthed following the several interpretations given to the publication of Charles Darwin’s evolutionary theory of (1859) that as of present, the world pattern, views, perception as to the value attached to human life has changed drastically from peace to war, love to hate, brotherliness to enmity and from moral to amoral. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Ikhayere (2023) posit that “an underdeveloped society or country is characterized by backwardness, primitiveness, tribalism, dependency, neo-colonialism, non-liberalism, exploitation, late capitalism, lack of modern differentiated industries, state of poverty in the society, the domination of foreign capital in the hands of foreign and local bourgeoisie or local comprador, low technology, low level politics, including social and cultural development” Lest we forget we are first and foremost the children of God whose identity is love before our tribe, beliefs, religion, socialization and civilization. We own to this God some reverence, loyalty, fear and respect for from him we came and unto Him we shall all return after our sojourn on earth as contained in the two major Abrahamic religions (Christianity and Islam).

Statement of the Problem

There has been a long-time debate on whether Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory has actually influenced Christianity, moral ethics and political thinking or not. While some opined that his Book on evolution gave birth to the audacity of the present wave of moral bankruptcy and decadence in the world, others are of the view that man can live without God. Is his theory questioning the omniscience and the omnipotence nature of God over creation? Is the concept of God an illusory or abstract imagination? Can man live the way he likes as an evolving being without recourse to God? While the issues of the influence of Darwin's evolutionary theory on Christianity and morality was added at the later part of 19th century debate the issue of morality in international relation has been on even before Darwin was born as the debate on idealism and realism in international politics dates back to the classical political theorists, Thucydides (C. 460–C. 400 B.C.E).

A century and a half after the publication of *The Origin of Species*, which Darwin was skeptical to publish, it's difficult for us today to appreciate the seismic shift in attitudes that began with its publication. Most of us have grown up having been taught Darwin's theory from our elementary schools. Many people accept it unquestioningly. Few questioned the teaching of his ideas in our public schools without much ado and now its application is in almost every field of human endeavours. Today, its applications are different from what it was in (1859). Richard Weikart, head of the history department at California State University, Stanislaus, describes how some viewed the book's initial publication: In his words "A good deal of the initial resistance to Darwinism sprang from a perceived threat to the moral order". Adam Sedgwick, Darwin's former mentor in natural science at the University of Cambridge, expressed this fear poignantly in a letter he wrote to Darwin in (1859), shortly after reading 'The Origin of Species'. He stated, '*Passages in your book...greatly shocked my moral taste*'" (From Darwin to Hitler, 2004, p. 1); warning of the consequences of the book's publication, Sedgwick added that "*humanity, in my mind, would suffer a damage that might brutalize it, and sink the human race into a lower grade of degradation than any into which it has fallen since its written records tell us of its history*" (From Darwin to Hitler, 2004, p. 1)

Today, the moral and Christian doctrine's attack which started then has gradually gotten to a point that twenty-three (23) countries have at the moment adapted same sex marriage as against Biblical teachings and moral laws. As of June 2025, same-sex marriage is legal in many countries. In Europe we have: **Netherlands** (2001), **Belgium** (2003), **Canada** (2005), **Spain** (2005), **Norway** (2002), **Sweden** (2006), **Portugal** (2017), **Denmark** (2012), **Finland** (2017) **Ireland** (2015), **Luxembourg** (2015), **Malta** (2017), **Germany** (2017), **Iceland** (2010), **Slovenia** (2022). Among the American countries we have: **Canada** (2005), **Argentina** (2010), **United States** (2015), **Mexico** (2010), **Colombia** (2016) and **Uruguay** (2013). In Oceania, we have: **Australia** (2017) and in Africa we have **South Africa** (2006) and their defense is premised on Charles Darwin's theory of evolution.

Prior to the publication of Darwin's "*Origin of Species*" in (1859), the field of evolutionary was nearly non-existent. No sooner the book was published, evolutionary theory and its associated applications soon became the focus of intense activity, and today a vast literature, including entire periodicals exists which are devoted to this field and its various specialties. Darwin's theory of evolution based upon natural selection changed the thinking of countless fields of study from biology to anthropology. His work established that "evolution" had occurred: not necessarily that it was by natural or sexual selection but by gradual change and development. In many senses, Darwin's theories created a societal transformation. In other word, Darwin's theory consisted of two main points; i) diverse groups of animals evolve from one or a few common ancestors; ii) the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is natural selection (<https://www.sparknotes.com/biology/evolution/darwin/summary/> retrieved on 4/06/25).

By the time of Darwin's death in (1882), the fact of evolution was almost universally accepted by his contemporaries, the mechanism for this evolution. However, the theory of natural selection did not become orthodoxy until long after his death. Enthused by Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory where the world is right now, the level of moral bankruptcy could not have been imagined in the days of Charles Darwin and one wonders where the world is heading. The moral suasion of the Bible which is now being called to question among others is what this article intends to bring to the fore in the course of this researched articles.

Purpose of the study

The study seeks to: i). Examine Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory and its impact on Christianity and morality; ii) Identify the major crusader of the war against Christianity and morality; iii) Recommend possible approach to achieving positive world order.

Charles Darwin's biography

Charles Darwin was born in Shrewsbury, Shropshire, England, on February 12, 1809, at the family home, the Mount House. He was the fifth of six children of Robert Darwin and Susannah Darwin the daughter of Wedgwood. In 1825, Darwin went to Edinburgh University to study medicine then theology, but his revulsion at the brutality of surgery led him to neglect his medical studies. In 1827, his father, unhappy that his younger son would not become a physician, enrolled him in a Bachelor of Arts course at Christ's College, University of Cambridge, which would qualify him to be a clergyman. At Cambridge, Darwin preferred riding and shooting to studying. He was later introduced to the Reverend John Stevens Henslow, professor of botany, for expert advice on beetles. Darwin subsequently joined Henslow's natural history course, becoming the "favorite pupil," known as "the man who walks with Henslow." (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online : <https://darwin-online.org.uk> > biography retrieved on June 12, 2025).

Inspired by Alexander von Humboldt's *Personal Narrative*, he planned to visit Madeira to study natural history in the tropics with some classmates after graduation. To prepare for this project, Darwin now joined the geology course of the Reverend Adam Sedgwick, then during the summer break worked with him at mapping strata in Wales. Darwin was surveying strata in Wales on his own when his plans to visit Madeira were dashed by a message that his intended companion had died. Before then, Henslow had recommended Darwin for the unpaid position of gentleman's companion to Robert FitzRoy, the captain of HMS *Beagle*, on a two-year expedition to chart the coastline of South America which would give Darwin valuable opportunities to develop his career as a naturalist. His father objected to the voyage, regarding it as a waste of time, but was persuaded by Josiah Wedgwood to agree to his son's participation. This voyage became a five-year expedition that would change science dramatically. In his lifetime, Charles

Darwin gained international fame as a pre-eminent scientist (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online: <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025)

However, from 1837 onwards, Darwin was repeatedly incapacitated with illnesses ranging from stomach pains, vomiting, severe boils, palpitations, trembling, and other symptoms, which particularly affected him in times of stress, when attending meetings, or dealing with controversy over his theory. While organizing *Zoology* and correcting proofs of his *Journal*, Darwin's health suffered major setbacks. On September 20, 1837, he suffered "palpitations of the heart" and left for a month of recuperation in the countryside (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online: <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025).

Upon being fully recuperated, Darwin returned home to Shrewsbury. Pondering his career and prospects, he drew up a list with columns headed "Marry" and "Not Marry." Having come down in favor of marrying, he discussed it with his father, and then went to visit his cousin Emma on July 29, 1838. Charles chose to marry his first cousin Emma Wedgwood. He did not get around to proposing, but against his father's advice he told her of his ideas on transmutation. On November 11, 1838, he returned and proposed to Emma, telling her his ideas. He eventually got married to Emma Wedgwood on 29 January, 1839 at St. Peter Anglican Church ceremony. The Darwin's had ten children, three of whom died early. These were: William Erasmus Darwin (December 27, 1839 – 1914) Anne Elizabeth Darwin (March 2, 1841 – April 22, 1851) Mary Eleanor Darwin (September 23, 1842 – October 16, 1842)Henrietta Emma "Etty" Darwin (September 25, 1843 – 1929) George Howard Darwin (July 9, 1845 – December 7, 1912) Elizabeth "Bessy" Darwin (July 8, 1847 – 1926) Francis Darwin (August 16, 1848 – September 19, 1925) Leonard Darwin (January 15, 1850 – March 26, 1943) Horace Darwin (May 13, 1851 – September 29, 1928) Charles Waring Darwin (December 6, 1856 – June 28, 1858). Several of their children suffered illness or weaknesses, and Charles Darwin's fear that this might be due to the closeness of his and Emma's lineage was expressed in his writings on the ill effects of inbreeding and advantages of crossing.

Darwin died in Downe, Kent, England, on April 19, 1882 and buried in Westminster Abbey close to Sir William Herschel and Sir Isaac Newton (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online : <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025) .

Theoretical framework

Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which was published in 1859 is the theoretical framework for this article. This became necessary as it is the influence of this theory that is the basis of the discussion under consideration. Considered the "father of evolutionary theory," Darwin made two contributions of enormous impact to the idea of evolution in his theory. First, Darwin marshaled substantial evidence for the theory of descent with modification, a kinematic theory that treats non-causal relations between things which deals with the pattern of evolution. The second is, Darwin's theory of natural selection. This dynamic theory that involves mechanisms and causal relationships deals with the process of evolution which consisted of two main points: (i) Diverse groups of animals evolve from one or a few common ancestors; and (ii) the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is by natural selection. <https://www.sparknotes.com/>.

Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory established that "evolution" had occurred: not necessarily that it was by natural or sexual selection but through diverse groups of animals evolving from one or a few common ancestors and that the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is by natural selection and had nothing to do with God or man. These claims negate the biblical teachings of God being the author of life. By the time of Darwin's death in 1882, the fact of evolution was almost universally accepted by his contemporaries and disciples. According to Idehen and Oaikhena (2021), "stable policies and strong institutions are crucial elements of an enabling environment, which, is necessary for thriving prosperous economy".

Of course, innumerable developments in evolutionary theory have taken place since the time of Darwin, and some of Darwin's concepts have proven wrong. Darwin accepted both the principle of use and disuse (Lamarck's "First Law") and the formulation of inheritance of acquired characteristics (Lamarck's "Second Law"). In *The Origin of*

Species, he stated that "there can be little doubt that use in our domestic animals strengthens and enlarges certain parts and disuse diminishes them; and that such modifications are inherited." Indeed, Darwin devoted an entire section in chapter 5 to the concept of use and disuse (Bull, 1995).

The second concept is the concept of mind mutation. The world is being turned upside down or downside up by the major world players and the weaker world may not be able to stop them and may be forced to join them. Be it known today that the end is near either in line with Biblical predictions or by man's scientific inquisitiveness and invention. It may be recalled that covid-19 experiment and adventures wherein the world was brought to its knees, is still very fresh as it affects survival of the fittest principle. The Covid-19 experience and experiment coupled with human being married to animals are the effects of 'mind mutation' with its root from Darwin's evolutionary theory. The concept states that: *the mind infinitely mutates infinitely towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively* (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting (mutating) to it infinitely, be it good or bad. The present moral bankruptcies are some of the byproducts of the negative implications and applications of Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which is thus interpreted to mean 'the end justifies the means by the likes of Micaville and Hitler. This is nothing but the aftermaths of what this study called 'mind mutation' from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of survival of the fittest.

Mind mutation from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory

The mind mutation model/theory holds that just as diseases like malaria and typhoid mutates and becomes more resistant to drugs, plants mutate to produce better yielding and disease resistant species and organisms including humans also mutates to bring about resistant off springs; so do human mind mutates over time which is parts of what the advanced world called new world order? It is what is called new world order, which takes its root from the Darwin's theory of 1859, called mind mutation. The theory/model further says that: *the mind infinitely mutates towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively* (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting (mutating) to it infinitely, be it good or bad. In other words, if one continues to do evil for

so long; the mind keeps adapting and adjusting towards the direction you so trained it. If for good, the mind keeps turning like radio receptive chip and get to a level that the individual seamlessly do good and naturally abhors evil; and if for bad, the mind over time tastes for evil naturally. It is the law of the mind as contained in proverbs 4:23 and Romans 1:28.

This applies to the individual, the community, states and nations in international relations and world politics. The major players in international politics (the developed world) have reached the level of infinite mind mutation negatively as anything moral is seen as weakness, and amoral behavior is seen as strength, freedom and superiority.

See model/theory of mind mutation.

The concept of mind mutation berthed from Charles Darwin’s evaluation theory
Authors design 2025

The Bible mentions bestiality in four different passages. Exodus 22:19 says, “Anyone who has sexual relations with an animal must be put to death.” Leviticus

18:23 declares, "Do not have sexual relations with an animal and defile yourself with it. A woman must not present herself to an animal to have sexual relations with it; that is a perversion." Leviticus 20:15-16 commands, "If a man has sexual relations with an animal, he must be put to death, and you must kill the animal. If a woman approaches an animal to have sexual relations with it, kill both the woman and the animal. They must be put to death; their blood will be on their own heads." Deuteronomy 27:21 agrees, "Cursed is the man who has sexual relations with any animal." From these verses, it is abundantly clear that, according to the Bible, bestiality is a horrible, unnatural, and abominable sin.

Why is bestiality condemned so strongly? First, it is an unnatural perversion. Clearly, human beings were designed/intended to mate with other human beings, not animals. Anything outside this Biblical injunction is against morality, God and reduces man to a beast. In the creation account, none of the animals were "suitable" for Adam (Genesis 2:20). Second, bestiality represents the ultimate of sexual deviancy. The fact that the animal was to be put to death (Leviticus 20:15-16), despite the fact that the anima(s) may be "innocent," indicates how wickedly perverse bestiality is. Third, and perhaps most importantly, bestiality essentially denies the uniqueness of humanity which God created in His image (Genesis 1:27). Bestiality lowers humanity to nothing more than an animal, a beast which is unable to distinguish right from wrong, natural from unnatural, love from lust and good from evil.

The New Testament nowhere mentions bestiality by name, but that should not be interpreted as an allowance for bestiality or a weakening of God's moral standards. Bestiality is by definition included in Scripture's many prohibitions against sexual immorality as contained (1 Corinthians 6:9; Galatians 5:19; Colossians 3:5; Hebrews 13:4).

What about gay marriage? It is the height of moral bankruptcy and an affront against God who could have, but did not; create man for man. He knew that man could not procreate with man. Beyond the pleasure of sexual intimacy, God's intention for creating the woman for man is for procreation (Genesis 2:18). Today, it therefore will shock the moral taste of any man in the image of God to learn that "Gay marriage is legal in 6 states and having sex with a horse is legal in 23 states in America!." This should shock the moral taste of any religious or moral minds.

Methodology

The researcher employed library research methodology to explore the relevant literatures on the influence of Charles Darwin's Evolutionary Theory on Christianity and morality in the 21st century international relations. This method was seen to be appropriate as it allowed for in-depth, extensive and comprehensive examination of the existing relevant books, journals, texts, newspapers and scholarly articles on Darwin, his theory of evolution as it relates to Christianity, morality and international relations. By reviewing a wide range of literatures, key concepts and theories, this study was able to identify areas where Darwin's evolutionary theory have influenced Pseudo-Christianity and morality in international relations; synthesize the discussions and findings as well as generate incisive enquiries that could inform and affect future studies in its recommendations.

Discussion

Where did Darwin's ideas and theory lead? who was Charles Darwin? Devil or Angel, Christian or Atheist, a radical who wanted to destroy society or Conservative, can we separate his scientific idea from who he was as a person?

These can be looked upon from two perspectives viz: Moral cum religion and political. Enthused with his new theory, it's doubtful that Charles Darwin gave much thought to the possible moral consequences of what he was writing. What actually happened was that evolution was promoted as a faith. Galton hoped that eugenics would one day have the authority of the church. Haeckel set up his "Monist League" explicitly in order to found an "evolutionary religion". And, for Huxley, trans-humanism was quite obviously a religion-substitute.

In fact, evolution may have been seen as progress, however progress is understood if I understood what progress means. But the confusion of the two is probably incurable. It expresses a central illusion of modern times - the myth that scientific knowledge can enable the human species to seize control of its destiny. The lesson of Darwinism is that species have no collective purpose. It is not "humanity" that uses the results of scientific inquiry. Instead, some human beings use science to control others.

Happily, and fortunately too, no group is likely ever going to be able to control humankind as a whole. Huxley's vision will remain no more than an ugly dream. Yet the appeal of this fantasy is unlikely to wane, because it satisfies the need of the amoral faith while offering the alluring prospect of power. Darwin certainly could not have foreseen that less than 75 years later, his ideas would lead to Adolf Hitler and the Holocaust, the Nazi attempt at exterminating the Jews. But Professor Weikart's detailed book documents the connection, with plenty of quotes from mostly German philosophers and scientists in the intervening years.

Dr. Richard Evans, professor of modern history at the University of Cambridge and author of *The Coming of the Third Reich*, says that Weikart's book "shows in sober and convincing detail how Darwinist thinkers in Germany had developed an amoral attitude to human society by the time of the First World War, in which the supposed good of the race was applied as the sole criterion of public policy and 'racial hygiene.'" "Without oversimplifying the lines that connected this body of thought to Hitler, he demonstrates with chilling clarity how policies such as infanticide, assisted suicide, marriage prohibitions, and much else were being proposed for those considered racially or eugenically inferior by a variety of Darwinist writers and scientists, providing Hitler and the Nazis with a scientific justification for the policies they pursued ..." (Richard, 2004).

Many have asked how the nation that produced Beethoven, Bach, Goethe and Schiller could have allowed a man like Hitler to become their supreme leader. Weikart's research helps us understand how this happened, by showing the gradual change in thinking that took place "from Darwin to Hitler"—a degeneration in appreciating the value of human life that continues to this day. In Nigeria today, Boko Haram, Fulani Herdsmen, ritualists, cultists etc, could be slaughtering human beings on camera with dignity and effrontery without any moral guilt or feelings that differentiate human from beasts! It wasn't only Hitler's National Socialist (Nazi) movement that was heavily influenced by Darwin. "After reading Darwin's *Origin of Species*, Karl Marx [the founder of the communist movement] wrote to Friedrich Engels, 'Although developed in a coarse English manner, this is the book that contains the foundation in natural history for our view.'" Furthermore, many pacifists, feminists, birth control advocates, and homosexual rights activists some of whom were

persecuted and even killed by the Nazis—were enthusiastic Darwinists and used Darwinian arguments to support their political and social agendas” (Richard Weikart, 2004).

Consequent upon Darwin’s theory, a whole new scale of national state was clearly on the horizon for the 20th C—Russia and the U.S. These had larger populations (over 100 million each—Britain a little over 40 million, France about 60 million, Germany over 60 million) and enormous resources; they were in fact continental powers. Russia had always been larger than other European states, but the size had been offset by the fact that Russia was very backward in industrial terms and thus in military terms also. However, by the 1890s, although still behind other parts of northern Europe, Russia was beginning to industrialize.

As it caught up industrially, Russia’s size would begin to have its impact in terms of power. The label for these new larger entities was ‘world power’. The problem nagging people in Germany, Britain and France was how would they get the additional resources i.e., like poker chips, to remain in the game. They were threatened with being reduced to ‘second class or second rate’ status. If you want to understand the frenzy for acquiring empire in the late 19th C, these concerns were probably more important than anything else; colonies were believed to provide extra resources, human and material, to keep European great powers in the game of world powers and the colonies who were regarded as the inferior race were to be used to service the European’s industrial needs. In his explanation of Darwin’s theory, Friedrich Ratzel (1844-1904) argued that national states were organisms and as such were subject to the same Darwinist pressures and requirements as other living organisms. This model carried many ramifications: nations were born, grew and matured; nations could also die. As with all organisms, nations require land, space, in order to survive. (<https://www.google.com/> 2025).

A new political order

Darwin’s ideas led to a radically different worldview on the part of many European thinkers. “In 1904 one of the leading German Darwinian biologists, Arnold Dodel, proclaimed, ‘The new world view actually rests on the theory of evolution. On it we have to construct a new ethics ... All values will be revalued’ ... Their moral relativism implied that some moral

values might have been valid in the past, but may no longer apply under modern conditions” (p. 43). Interestingly, a contemporary of Dodel, the famous American anti-evolutionist William Jennings Bryan, “was largely motivated by concern over the moral implications of Darwinism. As a pacifist, Bryan was outraged by the Darwinian rhetoric of German militarists, whom he held responsible for the outbreak of World War I” (p. 1). Bryan’s concerns were proven right, as their thinking was just a stepping-stone to Hitler’s racial theories leading to a second global conflict a quarter century later.

Besides, Darwin’s theory did not just alter political thinking, contributing to fascism, communism and two world wars. It also changed the thinking of huge numbers of people within Western societies on moral and Biblical teachings.

Values based on centuries of Judeo-Christian teaching on the sanctity of marriage and human life in general began to erode. Darwin’s theory did not just provide an alternative explanation to the biblical account of creation, it effectively led to doubts on *everything* in the Bible, including the moral laws. Today, many in the West view marriage as a quaint but outdated custom, while the idea of fidelity (sexual commitment) to one partner for life is held by only a small minority both in the western world and the world over. In the minds of many today, sex is solely for pleasure, and children are an inconvenience and a burden. Without realizing it, one of the inevitable consequences of Darwinism is the very real threat to the very existence of the human race as people who have embraced his teaching are increasing by the day.

Rejection of Judeo-Christian values

Weikart explains how accepting Darwinist dogma shifted society’s thinking on human life: “Before Darwinism burst onto the scene in the mid-nineteenth century, the idea of the sanctity of human life was dominant in European thought and law (though, as with all ethical principles, not always followed in practice). Judeo-Christian ethics proscribed the killing of innocent human life, and the Christian churches explicitly forbade murder, infanticide, abortion, and even assisted suicide. “The sanctity of human life became enshrined in classical liberal human rights ideology as ‘the right to life,’ which according to John Locke and the United States Declaration of Independence, was one of the supreme

rights of every individual” (p. 75) but things have changed. But that was to change, “Only in the late nineteenth and especially the early twentieth century did significant debate erupt over issues relating to the sanctity of human life, especially infanticide, euthanasia, abortion, and suicide. It was no mere coincidence that these contentious issues emerged at the same time that Darwinism was gaining in influence. Darwinism played an important role in this debate, for it altered many people’s conceptions of the importance and value of human life, as well as the significance of death” (<https://www.google.com/2025>).

Consequences from rejecting God in the practice of bestiality

This progression in Western thinking is not surprising to Biblical readers who are familiar with the Apostle Paul’s letter to the Romans, written 18 centuries before Darwin. In it, the apostle showed how people’s rejection of the true God, in spite of the abundant physical evidence of His existence all around them in His creation, led inevitably to the worship of *things* and, in turn, to casting off moral values and restraint. “For since the creation of the world God’s invisible qualities ... have been clearly seen, being understood from what has been made, so that men are without excuse. For although they knew God, they neither glorified him as God nor gave thanks to him ... Although they claimed to be wise, they became fools and exchanged the glory of the immortal God for images made to look like mortal man and birds and animals ... and worshiped and served created things rather than the Creator” (Romans 1:20-25, New International Version). In the ancient world, the peoples who rejected God soon found the need for something to replace Him. Thus, they came up with the pagan gods of their imaginations, many of which reflected man’s own blood-lust and sexual appetites that are so much the opposite of the true Creator of the Bible. Rejecting the true God also had social and sexual consequences, as Paul showed in subsequent verses. “For this reason, God gave them up to vile passions. For even their women exchanged the natural use for what is against nature. Likewise, also the men, leaving the natural use of the woman, burned in their lust for one another, men with men committing what is shameful, and receiving in themselves the penalty of their error which was due” (verses 26-27).

Just as man's earlier rejection of God led to throwing off morality, once societies began to reject the Bible as the inerrant Word of God, people no longer saw any justification for their nations to be governed by God's moral laws. Many enthusiastically embraced Darwin's theory as it gave them excuse and freedom to reject the moral and Biblical laws of God and live sexually liberated lives like animals. The world we live is right now in disarray and mankind no longer value the Biblical, ethical and moral laws as government of all continents are approving and applauding amoral tendencies such as same sex marriage, killing, suicide, war, hatred, infanticide, love for money, survival of the fittest, marriage between human and animal like cat, dog and horse and ridiculing Biblical principles of value for human life, love, humility, righteous living, care for the weak, the widows, the fatherless, the voiceless, the orphans, victims of war, care for strangers, fairness, justice and the ultimate final destination of man either in hell with the devil or in heaven with God. It's now part of the new world order in America and other so called developed world.

Dr. Richard Evans, professor of modern history at the University of Cambridge and author of *The Coming of the Third Reich*, says that Weikart's book "shows that "Without over-simplifying the lines that connected this body of thought to Hitler, he demonstrates with chilling clarity how policies such as infanticide, assisted suicide, marriage prohibitions, same sex marriage, abortion and much else were being proposed for those considered racially or eugenically inferior by a variety of Darwinist writers and scientists, providing Hitler and the Nazis with a scientific justification for the policies they pursued ..." (From Darwin to Hitler, back cover).

Today, it's no longer secret that in America and Indian human and animals are now having carnal knowledge and cohabiting in marriage. In 2014, California Allows First-Ever State Recognized Human-Animal Marriage. National Report in San Francisco says history was made at the Chapel of Our Lady at the Presidio in San Francisco as the first-ever state recognized human-animal marriage took place. Local resident 35-year-old Paul Horner was the groom during the ceremony. Joining him was his faithful dog Mac who is 36-years-old in dog years. Paul Horner, a 35-year-old local resident, was the groom during the wedding ceremony. He was joined in 'unholy' matrimony with Mac, his faithful dog.

Again, on 11th Oct 2017, independent newspaper published that 43-year-old Wilhelmina Morgan Callaghan, from Northern Ireland, married her dog Henry eight years ago! In 2005, another British woman reportedly married a dolphin. The Sudanese goat marriage incident made headlines in 2006, when a man was forced to marry a goat after being caught in a sexual interaction with it. Other reports of human animal marriage include animals such as dogs, cats, frogs, and a dolphin.

A British woman, Amanda Rodgers, made headlines with her unique take on marriage. Her story became a sensation when she wed her beloved dog, Sheba, in a grand ceremony witnessed by 200 people in Croatia on 29 Oct 2023.

India with its vast rural population is a source for many of these stories. Recently the British Broadcasting Cooperation (BBC) ran an article entitled “Man ‘marries’ dog to beat curse.” As promised, it celebrates the marriage of one Selvakumar, a 33-year-old man, to a dog called Selvi in a village in Tamil Nadu. The marriage was intended to cure the groom of paralysis, which the villagers believed has resulted from his having killed dogs. It’s fun to read about the man who was forced to marry a goat in Sudan — a somewhat tragic story since his goat-wife apparently died soon after when she choked on a piece of plastic — but when a Western media organization reports on the odd happenings in parts of the developing world, is there an implicit moral judgment? Yes, it's true that in 2007, a man in Tamil Nadu, India, named P. Selvakumar, "married" a dog named Selvi in a traditional Hindu ceremony to ward off a perceived curse, as reported by NBC_News and the BBC.

In America today, in the name of freedom, civilization and socialization, parents can no longer control their children anymore else the child will call the police and the government will dispossess the parents of the child on the accusation of child abuse as is currently the case in most so-called civilized world. There is therefore the urgent need to raise alarm as in the novel ‘Things Fall Apart by a Nigerian novelist Chinua Achebe. Like a movie, it appears anything goes in developed countries as "Gay marriage is legal in 6 states. Having sex with a horse is legal in 23 states in America." Four states such as Hawaii, New Mexico, West Virginia and Wyoming do not have laws that formally prohibit sexual abuse of animals, traditionally known as bestiality.

Early societies responded to bestiality in various ways. In some, such as ancient Greece, sex between humans and nonhuman animals not only went unpunished, but it was possibly commonplace (Miletski, 2005). Other societies, however, punished bestiality severely. The first known bestiality laws were established by another ancient civilization, the Anatolian Hittites, who inscribed their legal code on clay tablets. The tablets, which are estimated to date from 1650 B.C.E. to 1500 B.C.E., also contain an array of rules related to the treatment of animals (Gordon S.2015). Similar to Hammurabi's code, many Hittite laws treat animals as property with economic value and provide for recompense if one's animal is injured or killed. Unlike Hammurabi's code, the Hittites specifically address bestiality in two of their approximately 200 rules. The first rule states: *If anyone has sexual relations with a pig or a dog, he shall die. He shall bring him to the palace gate. The king may have them killed or he may spare them, but the human shall not approach the king. If an ox leaps on a man, the ox shall die; the man shall not die. They shall substitute one sheep for the man and put it to death. If a pig leaps on a man, it is not an offense* (Roth, Hoffner, and Michalowski, 1995).

The second rule states: *If anyone has sexual relations with either a horse or a mule, it is not an offense, but he shall not approach the king, nor shall he become a priest. If anyone sleeps with an a married-woman, and also sleeps with her mother, it is not an offense* (Roth, et al, 1995).

The Hittite laws regarding bestiality offer a glimpse into the legislative motivation of the Hittite rulers and their society's views regarding animals in general. It is note-worthy that the laws regarding bestiality does not consider the animal's economic value. If they did, they would not proscribe death for an ox that "leaps on a man" in sexual excitement. On the contrary, there are some other value systems at play defining the animals for which bestiality is punishable. The array of punishments ranges from death for the human, the animal, or both; to nothing; or to some middling social sanction preventing one from becoming a priest. One legal scholar has suggested that the Hittite society developed rules related to sexual activity with animals based on the concept of cleanliness (Bryce, 2002). Sexual acts thought to put the community at risk of disease were defined as *hurkel* and therefore forbidden.

The texts of modern-day religions provide a window into how other early societies viewed bestiality. The Torah, known as the Pentateuch in the Christian tradition, composes the first five books of the Hebrew and Christian Bibles. The Torah is thought to have been completed by 400 B.C.E. and to express the beliefs and traditions of the Israelites, who lived in the Near East around 600 B.C.E. (Blenkinsopp, 1992). One of the books of the Torah, Leviticus, expressly forbids acts of bestiality: *Do not have sexual relations with an animal and defile yourself with it. A woman must not present herself to an animal to have sexual relations with it; that is a perversion. (Leviticus 18:23) (The Holy Bible. New Revised Standard Version, Catholic Edition.* Leviticus 20:15 states: *If a man has sexual relations with an animal, he shall be put to death; and you shall kill the animal (The Holy Bible. New Revised Standard Version, Catholic Edition).*

According to the Israelites, bestiality represented, a forbidden relationship. One was meant to give up his or her life rather than engage in such activity. The concern regarding defilement or, in other translations, “becoming unclean” (The Holy Bible. New International Reader’s Version) suggests that the Israelites had concerns like the Hittites’ regarding cleanliness or the risk posed to their society by sexual acts involving animals. Bestiality’s condemnation in the Bible likely affected societal responses to sexual acts involving animals for centuries. As scripture became a source of moral and ethical guidance for followers of Judeo-Christian religions, violations of rules in the Bible could be used as grounds to morally condemn and prosecute such behavior. From the fifteenth to seventeenth centuries in England and mainland Europe, the punishment for “buggery” was death for both human and nonhuman parties (Fudge, 2000).

One historian note that, “his disgusting crime appears to have been very common” (Evans, 2013). Such harsh, moralistic punishment was imported to the American colonies. The execution of Thomas Grainger in Plymouth Colony in 1642 serves as a clear example of moral punishment as a motivation for legal action. At the age of 16 or 17, Grainger was sentenced to death for “buggery” involving “a mare, two goats, five sheep, two calves, and a turkey” (Brandfold, and Morison, 1952). The animals were reportedly killed in front of Grainger, then thrown into a pit. Grainger was then hanged. Clearly, whatever moral harms

resulted from Grainger's acts of bestiality was thought to override any potential economic value of the animals with which he had sex.

The religious or moral condemnation of bestiality remains evident as a motivation for legislation in the names of statutes in some jurisdictions of the United States. For example, Maryland's law is entitled "unnatural or perverted sexual practice" (Maryland Criminal Code, 2002). North Carolina's law is named "crime against nature" (North Carolina General Statutes, 1994) and simply states, "If any person commits a crime against nature, with mankind or beast, he shall be punished as a Class I felon."

The law seemingly criminalizes anal intercourse, including consensual anal intercourse between two adult humans and the host of other sexual acts that humans may commit with animals. The problem at the moment is that these laws have been compromised in the same united states and other so called developed world and this article seeks to point to the inherent danger this poses to the human race, moral codes and laws including the Bible and an affront against the almighty God. From the above, just as the Holy Bible provide the foundation for moral behaviour so do Darwin's theory provided the foundation for amoral tendencies today.

In the discipline of international relations there are contending general theories or theoretical perspectives. Realism, also known as political realism, is a view of international politics that stresses its competitiveness and power (amoral). It is usually contrasted with idealism or liberalism, which tends to emphasize cooperation (moral). Realists consider the principal actors in the international arena to be states, which are concerned with their own security, ego and interest and so act in pursuit of their own national interests, and struggle for power and protection as pressure groups. The negative side of the realists, emphasizes on power and self-interest. The realists are often skeptical regarding the relevance of ethical and Biblical norms to relationship among states. The realists do not really care about justice but concerned about how to use strength and resources to dominate in the conflict among states which agrees with Darwin's theory of survival of the fittest. Some of the apostles of Darwinism are theorists as Reinhold Niebuhr, Hans Morgenthau and Machiavelli who were radical or extreme realism. Their doctrine involves the glorification of war or conflict in international politics and that "anything is

justified by reason of state” as their belief is that only the fittest should survive and the weak should be eliminated (Bull 1995).

They are rather critical of morals which they regarded as abstract discourse that does not take into account political realities. They assign supreme value to successful political action based on prudence and the ability to judge the rightness of a given action from among possible alternatives on the basis of its likely political consequences. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) asserted that “it is imperative to integrate strategies to deal with eradicating poverty and implementing adequate policies geared towards equitable distribution of resources, wealth and income that could easily lead to social protection coverage”. Realism encompasses a variety of approaches and claims a long theoretical tradition. Among its founding fathers are: Thucydides, Machiavelli and Hobbes.

Nevertheless, twentieth-century classical realism has today been largely replaced by neo-realism, which is an attempt to construct a more scientific approach to the study of international relations. Both classical realism and neo-realism have long been subjected to criticism from international relation theorists representing liberal and post-modern perspectives in line with Christian doctrines and morality. Yet, the damage of Darwin’s theory on the mind of the developed world as it affects the world’s moral psyche and Christianity is better imagined than experienced.

Given the above model, realism aligned with the amoral (Negative thoughts: Hate, war, rape, infanticide, suicide, kidnapping, killing, etc) which the developed world represents and the idealist aligned with the Biblical/Christian teachings and moral laws (Positive thoughts: love, mercy, justice, love, kindness, fairness, affection, forgiveness and cooperation etc) which the third world countries crave for.

Prudence, and not conviction of one’s own moral or ideological superiority, should guide political action. This is stressed in the fifth principle, where Morgenthau again emphasizes the idea that all state actors, including our own, must be looked at solely as political entities pursuing their respective interests defined in terms of power. By taking this point of view vis-à-vis its counterparts and thus avoiding ideological confrontation, a state

would then be able to pursue policies that respected the interests of other states, while protecting and promoting its own.

Insofar as power, or interest defined as power, is the concept that defines politics, politics is an autonomous sphere, as Morgenthau says in his sixth principle of realism. It cannot be subordinated to ethics. However, ethics does still play a role in politics. "A man who was nothing but 'political man' would be a beast, for he would be completely lacking in moral restraints. A man who was nothing but 'moral man' would be a fool, for he would be completely lacking in prudence" (12). Political art requires that these two dimensions of human life, power and morality, be taken into consideration. (*First published Mon Jul 26, 2010; substantive revision Wed May 24, 2017*). *A man without religious inclination will act ruthlessly, brutal and not be different from beast. Here lies the burden of the need to align with moral and Biblical ethics if the society must be ordered in line with God's plan for humanity. A man is both physical and spiritual being and it's this spiritual nature of man that differentiate man from other lower being for GOD said" Let us make man in our own image after our likeness (Gen. 1:26) but could not say so while creating other beings.*

Recommendation

The world is being turned upside down or downside up by the major world players and the weaker world may not be able to stop them and may be forced to join them. Be it known today that the end is near either in line with Biblical predictions or by man's scientific inquisitiveness and invention. It may be recalled that covid 19 experiment and adventures wherein the world was brought to its knees is still very fresh as it affects survival of the fittest principle. The Covid 19 experience and experiment coupled with human being married to animals are the effects of 'mind mutation' with its root from Darwin's evolutionary theory. The present moral bankruptcies are some of the byproducts of the negative implications and applications of Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which is thus interpreted to mean 'the end justifies the means by the likes of Micaville and Hitler. This is nothing but the aftermaths of what I called 'mind mutation' from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of survival of the fittest.

Conclusion

Political realism is usually contrasted by IR scholars with idealism or liberalism, a theoretical perspective that emphasizes international norms, interdependence among states, and international cooperation. Can international politics be based on a moral order derived from the principles of justice, Biblical teachings or will it forever remain in the arena of conflicting national interests and power based on survival of the fittest? Will morality and Christianity be eroded and the world will not be brought to its knees with the survival of the fittest theory?

Although Darwin thought Man's innate nobility would predispose him kindly towards the sick and poor – or perhaps those who think or look differently from ourselves, his successors tended to have no such scruples. The bulk of Sewell's book is taken up with the colorful history of the eugenics movement, which, by the early 20th century, had managed to gain the approval of Parliament. The Mental Deficiency Act 1913 classified people as "idiots", "imbeciles", "the feeble-minded" and "moral defectives" and led to at least 50 years of people being locked up or lobotomized on the flimsiest pretenses. The concurrent situation across the Atlantic was similar; countless low-income Americans were sterilized under largely false pretenses on grounds of weak species.

A clear-eyed look at history shows us that tyrannies tend to go underground or become bit by bit so institutionalized that they are eventually "hidden in plain sight". One of the central beliefs of the eugenics movement was the superiority of western civilization, whose values would eventually eliminate "an endless number of the lower races" (Darwin's words). This is precisely the assumption behind the policies of the World Bank, whose loans restructure developing nations' cultures after capitalist, earth-plundering models and so on. Whatever you may think of the gentle, doubting man, Darwin's cold-blooded ideas continue to wreak havoc in our world and if care is not taken, man is already on his way to self-destruction.

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